

**Book Review of “*Social pedagogy for social inclusion and children's rights discourses*”, edited by A. Odrowaz-Coates,
Warsaw: Maria Grzegorzewska University Press 2022, pp. 130.**

Anna Koc [1]¹⁷

Abstract

Book review of “Social pedagogy for social inclusion and children's rights discourses” – edited volume 2022.

Keywords

Social pedagogy, social inclusion, special education, children’s rights, UNESCO

First submission: September 2022; Revised: October 2022, Accepted: November 2022

¹⁷ [1] Independent Researcher, ORCID: 0000-0001-6458-8956, e-mail: ak63514@aps.edu.pl

The *Social pedagogy for social inclusion and children's rights discourses* is another volume continuing the 11-year tradition of the UNESCO Janusz Korczak Chair's publishing series, whose aim is to disseminate inclusive international scientific exchange. The long-term work of so many researchers puts on the pedestal the mission of fostering social integration of children, based on international cooperation and a deep sense of respect for each culture or country. In turn, this international scientific cooperation shows the hegemony of the English language in political discourses, legal and political documents, in related media discourses but is also the medium of communication enabling inclusion, which creates a certain linguistic paradox (c.f. Odrowaz-Coates 2019). It does not come as a surprise as the editor is the proponent of this dual-dialectic perspective on the shared language of global communication.

The main goal of the contributors to the above volume is to get to know about the various social narratives formed around children's rights, their participation, the formation of the idea of childhood, and how they can support or deny the social integration of children and adolescents in socio-environmental contexts. Furthermore, the subject of this volume concerns issues of social pedagogy, education for social inclusion, special educational needs, and human rights, with particular emphasis on children's rights. This book presents national contexts from Canada, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Nigeria, Poland, Romania, and the USA with the faith to establish common ground for improving education and the social system.

Reconciling the Criticisms and Commendations in Children's Rights Education is the first of thirteen chapters, written by Kathleen Manion, a professor of humanitarian studies, and an associate professor at the Royal Roads University in Canada. She has worked in academia, government, and the not-for-profit sector within several countries. In her research, she has focused on children's rights, participation, education, and youth climate action. What is more, professor Manion's research and policy work have among others included the prevention of violence against children and families, youth justice, and child protection and wellbeing. Her monograph is devoted to children's rights. Professor Manion defines, assumes, and proves that the essence of social pedagogy is precisely children's rights. She describes how important a prudent collocation to balance rights is.

The second part of this book *Education and social vulnerability of students from disadvantaged backgrounds in Romania* is a presentation of the situation of students from vulnerable backgrounds in the Romanian educational context. This unit was written by two authors. The first of them is Doctor of Psychology Julien-Ferencz Kiss from the University of Oradea in Romania, whose lecturer is at the University of Oradea in Romania.

His main fields of research are the history of psychology, educational psychology, interindividual differences, and social vulnerability. The second author is Professor Florica Ortan who is the head of the teaching department at the University of Oradea. They both participated in a collaboration between seven European universities and covers health in 2021, and also have high achievements in their scientific fields. However, in this research, they are looking for the best method to remedy Romanian students' low results in overall educational outcomes. In this part, Dr. Kiss and Prof. Ortan are submitting an analysis of the evolution of school performance and the dropout rate of Romanian youth. They base their conclusion on analyse the data on school performance, which has fallen sharply over the last 10 years, and also at teachers' really important perspective on educational vulnerability. The following part refers to stereotypes and prejudices that affect contemporary society. Dr. Cosmin Blândul Valentin, the Doctor of pedagogy at the University of Oradea, brilliantly analyses here some stereotypes that may have

a negative influence on the life of a person whom we consider to be different from ourselves. He also points to forms of manifestation of these stereotypes, which allows for a closer acquaintance with a given problem.

The next chapter, written by Princewill Chukwuma Abakporo and Doctor of philosophy Stanley Timeyin Ohenhen from Bowen University Iwo in Nigeria, presents the multifaceted nature of the dissertation on the subject of rapid entry into adulthood of Nigerian children from the perspective of sociopsychology and drama.

The author of the subsequent monograph, Doctor Laurențiu Dragoș Mândrea from the University of Oradea in Romania, shows the importance of social pedagogy in the context of restorative justice and resocialization of young people in Romania. The following part is an interesting reflection on personal qualities observed in the development of vocabulary in English, which is a foreign language for hard-of-hearing children from Kazakhstan. To obtain the highest quality of the text, Saidaeva Bayan Mukhtarkyzy and Namazbaeva Zhamilya Idrisovna analyzed the work of scientists who deal with the methods used in language teaching and checked their quality in their practice, examining their strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, by relying on the pedagogical and psychological profile of 5th-grade students with hearing impairments, the methods of shaping lexical skills in English were established. This led the researchers to an important conclusion. Namely, it has been noticed that the increase in the number of students with hearing loss in a foreign language has a huge impact on the formation of the child's personality.

The seventh part of this book refers to the study of the professional training of a teacher in an inclusive education environment. The authors - Akbota.D. Zhumageldiyeva and prof. Galiya A. Abaeva from Kazakh National Pedagogical University, explain the current state, direction, and content of inclusive education based on foreign and domestic experiences. Researchers postulate the scientifically proven most effective methods of teaching, forms, and methods of shaping teachers' readiness to work with children with disabilities based on their competencies. *Ways to develop moral values of visually impaired students through folk music* is a contribution written by Асия Darkembayeva and Laura Butabayeva from Kazakhstani National Pedagogical University. The main aim of the article is to present the ways and possibilities of using folk music in the educational process of visually impaired students in shaping moral values. In addition to shown above research problem, it was discovered some positive results. This success will be the ability to freely grow up in the surrounding society as adults with the characteristics of their nation.

The chapter by Nurbyk Razukhan focuses on current policy actions toward inclusive education in Mongolia. The implemented activities to improve the legal environment of students with disabilities, activities aimed at improving the policy and strategy for teaching and learning children with disabilities, as well as activities for educating and continuous development of teachers in terms of working with children with disabilities in the inclusive education model are described. In addition, specific recommendations were made to improve the Mongolian Educational System to introduce equal access to quality education, and lifelong learning for every child, paying special attention to children with difficulties.

The following chapter is written by two Kazakhstani scholars, Adirbekova Zhanar Seitovna and Bekmuratova Gulzhanar Togyzbayevna from Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University. This is another chapter relating to the development of children with hearing impairments - this time students attending primary education in Kazakhstan are discussed.

Chapter Eleven discusses digital citizenship, labelling, and structuring the functional boundaries of an emergent phenomenon that crosses multiple domains of digital privacy. However, it should be strongly emphasized that the article doesn't deal with the use of metadata, as this belongs to a different branch of science. Professor Doctor Mark Juszczak from Collins College of Professional Studies at St. John's University in the USA focuses on the emerging phenomenon of the mandatory metadata regime. It also addresses the topic of how its inherent functional elements and structures exacerbate problems of structural inequality.

The final two parts deal directly with the subject of special educational needs and social inclusion within an educational setting. Researchers Kaipova Zhanat Mamurzhankyzy and Professor Bekmuratova Gulzhanar Togizbaevna, both from the Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology, KazNPU named after Abai in Kazakhstan, recommend special teachers to master new educational technologies and forms of work, due to the new, modernized model of special education. At the same time, great difficulty in working with children with special needs is the poorly developed technology and the lack of specialists in the new formation. Then, the authors of the last chapter, Nursaule Molbayeva and Galiya Abayeva from the Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University in Kazakhstan, summarize the current trends in Kazakhstani theory and practice of evaluating the learning outcomes of children with disabilities. They also put forward a hypothesis as to the basis for the emergence of threats in evaluation practices and current research areas for improving the educational achievements of students with disabilities.

To sum up, the book contains chapters oscillating in the field of special education, and social integration, with particular attention to students with disabilities or special educational needs. In addition, the issue of children's rights and the phenomena around them were also discussed in many contexts concerning a given country.

References

Odrowąż-Coates, A. (2019). *Socio-educational Factors and the Soft Power of Language: The Deluge of English in Poland and Portugal*. Lanham, New York; Rowman & Littlefield: Lexington Books.